

Table 1 Isotopic and chemical compositions of pore water in the sediment sequence at Site U1438

Sample	Top depth (m)	Bottom depth (m)	Average depth (m)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰)	stdev (‰)	δD (‰)	stdev (‰)	Salinity	pH	Cl (mM) IC	Na (mM) IC	Ca (mM) IC	Mg (mM) IC	SO_4^{2-} (mM, IC)	NH_4^+ (μM , IC)	Mn (μM) 257.6 nm ICPAES	Si (μM) 288.2 nm ICPAES
B01H4	2.90	3.00	2.95	-0.84	0.15	-4.50	0.68	36.5	7.22	557.40	479.57	11.51	52.57	28.70	292.0	186.45	483.54
B02H4	13.10	13.20	13.15	-0.97	0.35	-4.18	0.62	36.5	7.37	562.80	484.47	14.10	51.69	28.68	200.5	130.23	438.28
B04H4	32.10	32.20	32.15	-0.97	0.35	-4.18	0.62	37.5	7.33	567.40	485.15	17.54	48.92	28.29	256.5	115.35	477.18
B05H4	41.60	41.70	41.65	-0.93	0.26	-7.15	0.08	37.5	7.39	576.90	495.67	18.94	48.68	28.45	285.7	134.47	569.87
B06H4	51.10	51.20	51.15	0.33	0.72	-4.89	0.96	37.5	6.97	567.30	484.28	20.21	46.71	27.83	189.2	175.58	640.22
B07H4	60.60	60.70	60.65	-0.87	0.23	-7.75	0.21	37.0	6.84	567.20	483.49	21.51	45.32	27.66	152.5	199.00	694.69
B08H2	67.07	67.17	67.12	-0.43	0.14	-7.15	0.11	36.5	6.99	565.30	483.60	22.43	44.34	27.38	179.6	190.25	697.08
B09H4	79.60	79.70	79.65	-0.12	0.30	-6.60	0.22	36.5	7.11	566.80	482.14	23.76	44.37	27.15	184.2	165.51	407.84
B10H4	89.10	89.20	89.15	0.22	0.13	-6.87	0.45	36.5	7.40	566.20	478.54	25.34	44.89	26.89	163.6	181.77	322.28
B11H4	98.55	98.70	98.63	0.07	0.22	-3.43	0.88	36.0	6.80	563.80	472.64	27.10	43.99	26.48	127.1	194.57	262.29
B12H4	108.05	108.20	108.13	0.36	0.19	-3.85	1.55	36.5	7.11	564.00	471.59	29.12	43.03	26.38	143.8	204.82	256.52
B13H4	117.55	117.70	117.63	0.02	0.04	-4.04	0.33	36.0	6.96	560.40	461.72	32.10	52.78	26.35	221.8	246.84	331.96
B14H1	122.55	122.70	122.63	0.12	0.10	-3.56	0.53	36.0	6.74	554.30	462.62	32.13	41.60	26.02	194.3	264.87	595.47
B15H4	136.42	136.57	136.50	-0.24	0.19	-5.12	0.27	N/A	N/A	549.50	448.99	35.20	41.20	25.37	201.7	279.48	790.06
B16H3	144.55	144.70	144.63	-0.03	0.09	-6.12	0.38	36.0	7.38	548.10	445.33	37.65	40.28	25.20	205.0	277.52	515.09
B17H5	157.05	157.20	157.13	-0.42	0.10	-5.95	0.56	36.0	7.18	549.00	445.18	40.79	38.30	24.84	383.4	238.43	533.45
B18H3	163.55	163.70	163.63	-0.55	0.10	-4.90	0.71	36.5	7.06	560.60	460.01	41.78	35.25	25.25	131.7	199.54	684.25
B20F2	171.75	171.90	171.83	-1.95	0.12	-5.81	0.06	37.5	7.85	566.30	468.26	42.61	32.95	25.49	231.5	154.18	588.81
B23X3	184.95	185.10	185.03	-0.46	0.01	-3.89	0.21	36.5	8.04	568.20	466.98	45.86	31.27	25.55	311.7	133.62	613.77
B25X2	201.86	202.01	201.94	-0.78	0.16	-4.62	0.16	37.0	8.39	573.10	467.08	51.37	29.64	25.85	298.4	139.21	655.80
B26X3	213.15	213.30	213.23	-0.21	0.03	-5.26	0.60	36.5	8.52	571.20	464.21	52.00	28.32	25.37	149.2	122.81	656.75
B27X2	221.35	221.50	221.43	-0.95	0.13	-4.70	0.55	36.5	8.51	569.20	460.47	54.40	27.13	25.33	239.8	140.02	705.18
B28X3	232.40	232.55	232.48	-0.70	0.08	-4.17	0.30	36.5	8.34	570.40	459.81	56.08	27.12	25.11	93.2	148.86	783.78
B29X3	242.27	242.40	242.34	-0.51	0.06	-4.98	0.62	36.5	8.56	570.50	457.50	58.07	25.60	25.04	45.7	120.04	681.50
B30X5	254.95	255.10	255.03	-0.70	0.07	-4.69	0.33	37.5	8.69	572.10	456.73	60.56	24.85	24.83	53.2	116.13	720.10
D02R2	221.57	221.67	221.62	-1.66	0.14	-6.81	0.39	36.0	8.08	580.42	463.42	51.70	26.84	25.08	66.2	N/A	N/A
D04R1	230.80	230.95	230.88	-1.32	0.15	-5.55	0.71	37.0	8.81	583.39	466.02	53.71	26.57	25.64	74.3	107.88	714.91
D08R2	268.68	268.87	268.78	-1.73	0.18	-6.93	0.56	37.0	8.72	584.15	458.07	61.96	22.74	25.08	51.3	97.75	658.80
D09R1	278.31	278.50	278.41	-1.64	0.09	-5.81	0.47	37.5	9.20	584.55	456.13	63.41	21.98	24.85	60.2	60.82	512.97
D11R1	297.80	297.94	297.87	-1.43	0.05	-4.61	0.65	38.0	9.25	591.14	452.39	73.78	17.36	24.86	60.3	62.74	496.35
D13R2	318.52	318.64	318.58	-1.70	0.02	-6.99	0.31	38.0	8.53	591.24	444.38	78.77	15.74	24.83	52.9	72.71	613.17
D15R2	337.69	337.81	337.75	-1.27	0.13	-6.00	0.27	38.0	9.01	591.20	441.58	82.03	13.98	24.06	43.9	N/A	N/A

D18R1	365.38	365.51	365.45	-1.23	0.03	-5.81	0.11	39.0	9.06	599.07	423.26	99.43	8.17	22.20	59.2	N/A	N/A
D20R4	388.92	389.12	389.02	-1.42	0.06	-7.85	0.53	40.5	8.90	611.71	405.34	120.52	3.09	28.76	55.5	5.29	525.83
D25R3	436.53	436.71	436.62	-2.19	0.01	-7.26	0.46	41.0	N/A	614.07	376.32	138.92	1.00	20.55	72.2	13.32	191.26
D26R3	446.05	446.23	446.14	-2.00	0.13	-6.66	0.68	41.0	9.35	625.84	390.11	136.74	2.01	21.37	55.8	4.92	210.20
D28R5	465.93	466.08	466.01	-3.06	0.03	-7.32	0.07	41.0	9.54	627.95	369.10	150.94	0.34	21.00	26.3	1.54	215.03
D33R6	518.12	518.30	518.21	-3.34	0.02	-7.66	0.07	43.0	9.36	634.78	318.42	178.41	1.27	20.64	40.7	1.92	103.20
D35R5	535.20	535.40	535.30	-2.68	0.04	-9.71	0.27	44.0	9.40	640.00	273.80	205.51	N/A	20.58	67.8	1.44	112.41
D36R5	547.69	547.86	547.78	-2.57	0.06	-8.18	0.44	44.0	9.14	646.32	282.05	203.28	0.13	20.31	57.5	1.71	149.10
D37R2	551.43	551.58	551.51	-2.54	0.07	-8.34	0.38	44.0	9.52	643.66	299.13	193.28	0.19	20.07	34.0	0.31	119.67
D38R2	561.04	561.19	561.12	-2.90	0.20	-9.97	0.19	44.0	9.46	647.56	295.19	197.23	0.08	19.86	63.0	0.78	119.96
D39R5	574.77	574.92	574.85	-2.56	0.03	-9.83	1.04	44.0	9.33	658.04	293.84	203.04	1.03	20.86	35.9	0.87	164.89
D40R5	583.65	583.83	583.74	-2.51	0.10	-9.45	0.13	44.5	9.11	647.54	281.50	204.09	0.47	20.00	59.3	2.65	172.24
D41R4	593.07	593.22	593.15	-2.53	0.12	-10.54	0.45	45.0	9.76	651.97	248.13	222.72	0.50	20.15	37.1	0.88	99.91
D43R1	608.04	608.20	608.12	-2.31	0.06	-9.93	0.34	45.0	9.77	648.51	259.97	213.05	1.62	20.79	47.0	0.04	86.12
D45R6	633.85	634.02	633.94	-2.69	0.06	-10.40	0.33	45.0	9.88	659.45	247.85	226.36	0.02	19.60	46.1	N/A	99.74
D46R6	643.43	643.55	643.49	-3.15	0.24	-9.22	0.14	45.5	9.66	659.60	246.95	227.15	0.52	19.80	33.4	N/A	105.26
D48R5	661.52	661.70	661.61	-3.80	0.12	-9.59	0.36	46.0	9.78	662.92	205.40	250.57	N/A	19.83	46.5	N/A	113.41
D49R1	666.33	666.50	666.42	-4.89	0.20	-10.87	0.28	46.0	9.87	667.46	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	39.7	0.16	98.07
D50R2	676.18	676.37	676.28	-4.39	0.10	-9.41	0.26	46.0	9.95	665.97	206.73	250.67	N/A	19.18	30.2	0.16	94.59
D52R3	697.92	698.09	698.01	-3.70	0.08	-8.82	0.41	46.0	9.61	661.04	214.21	243.27	1.46	19.77	30.9	0.20	92.05
D53R6	710.31	710.46	710.39	-4.25	0.21	-10.17	0.31	N/A	N/A	666.15	215.43	243.82	2.05	20.02	82.8	N/A	N/A
D56R4	737.31	737.54	737.43	-3.88	0.22	-8.02	0.05	46.0	9.21	668.14	220.47	242.12	1.19	18.75	83.0	0.96	104.35
D58R5	759.17	759.32	759.25	-4.78	0.24	-9.32	0.50	46.0	9.78	669.91	191.84	257.68	0.06	18.14	68.7	0.47	89.21
D60R6	779.46	779.63	779.55	-4.40	0.16	-9.27	0.41	46.0	9.74	667.78	215.00	244.49	0.53	18.61	50.2	N/A	111.21
D62R2	792.44	792.64	792.54	-4.55	0.11	-11.00	0.22	46.0	9.61	672.75	200.62	253.52	0.48	18.00	61.1	0.19	96.87
D64R4	814.62	814.77	814.70	-4.31	0.28	-9.18	0.09	46.0	N/A	675.36	181.92	263.10	0.77	17.50	60.6	N/A	N/A
D66R4	834.64	834.83	834.74	-4.32	0.07	-9.57	0.43	47.0	9.50	669.11	165.50	268.20	0.51	16.06	77.9	0.45	101.02
D68R2	851.10	851.26	851.18	-4.40	0.19	-8.23	0.31	46.0	9.58	668.60	175.35	259.93	2.34	16.77	51.9	N/A	66.57
D71R1	878.68	878.82	878.75	-4.40	0.19	-8.23	0.31	46.0	9.18	675.61	209.38	245.67	4.98	17.59	43.3	1.25	199.60
E06R4	891.63	891.78	891.71	-4.54	0.04	-8.74	0.26	46.0	9.60	644.04	160.93	256.13	1.43	15.59	N/A	2.21	114.69
E07R5	902.26	902.41	902.34	-4.94	0.10	-10.81	0.25	47.0	9.67	644.24	127.13	272.35	0.00	14.93	N/A	1.35	104.64
E10R3	929.65	929.80	929.73	-5.53	0.02	-10.51	0.09	N/A	9.43	647.48	148.76	261.99	2.19	16.42	N/A	N/A	92.47
E12R3	948.99	949.15	949.07	-4.43	0.25	-12.55	0.21	47.0	N/A	642.03	143.50	260.06	0.73	14.38	N/A	N/A	N/A

Note: 1. Sample number refers to the location in a core. B1H4 stands for the 4th section of core 1 in the Hole B. H, X and R stand for drilling manner
2. IC: ion chromatography; ICP-AES: inductively coupled plasma–atomic emission spectroscopy; N/A: not available